

Freelancing Platform

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ABSTRACT

Freelancing is doing a job under contract rather than full employment. Usually, people who freelance are self-employed and for whom they will work and they decide for how long. Freelancing offers a lot of freedom and flexibility which regular jobs cannot. The freelancer can choose the type of the work, time of the day they can work and how long they work, a location they work and volume of work take on. The freelancer can control work relationships and control workload Platform freelancing has many websites and anyone can register as freelancers or job posters. The aim of this project is to develop a web application where various types of software developers and designers can collaborate with each other and work on business projects by sharing the code, solving issues in the code and as well as companies can hire freelancers.

Keywords: Full-stack Web development, freelancers, clients

1. Introduction

In today's world, many people are choosing freelancing because it gives them more control over their work and time. Freelancers can pick jobs that fit their skills and interests. Online freelancing platforms help them find clients easily. These platforms let freelancers talk to clients, manage tasks, and get paid safely. Freelancers can also improve their reputation by working with different clients and getting good reviews. Freelancers can find more jobs, grow their skills, and earn more money over time. By connecting freelancers with clients and offering valuable tools, these platforms create new opportunities for both sides.

This introduction explains how freelancing platforms help connect freelancers with clients. By looking at features, user reviews, and job trends, freelancers can choose the best platform to help them succeed. Freelancing offers a flexible way to work and build a career on their own terms.

2. Research Methodology

This project is about building an online freelancing platform that connects freelancers, clients, and administrators. Our goal is to make freelancing better for everyone. To understand what users need, we used a mix of methods to collect information. We talked to and surveyed ten people, including freelancers and clients, to learn about their experiences with current platforms. Their feedback helped us see what users liked, what they didn't like, and how we could improve. For building the platform, we used a full-stack approach, with MySQL as the database. This setup helps us manage the database well, create easy-to-use interfaces, and handle the server side effectively. We organized user information, like profiles, job postings, and messages, in a clear way in the MySQL database. Each type of user—freelancer, client, and administrator—has different access and features, making the platform easier to use. Participants tried the registration process and gave feedback, which helped us find any problems and make improvements. We also looked at other freelancing platforms to see what features they have and what they lack. This comparison helped us to decide what to include in our platform, focusing on important issues like job visibility, payment processing, and communication. By using user feedback, thorough testing, and careful design, we hope to create a freelancing platform that meets users' needs and supports a strong online freelance community.

3. Theory

The theory behind the online freelancing platform focuses on making user interactions and processes smooth for both freelancers and clients. When users visit the platform, they are first directed to a registration page where they can sign up as either a freelancer or a client. This step is important because it sets up different roles for users, each with its own features that an administrator can monitor. After users enter their information and complete registration, their data is safely stored in a MySQL database. This database keeps freelancer and client data separate, which helps in managing information and providing personalized experiences for each user type. Once registration is complete, users are taken to their personalized homepages. Freelancers get access to a dashboard where they can see job listings, manage applications, and track project progress. Clients, on the other hand, can post jobs, review freelancer applications, and manage ongoing projects. This role-specific design makes it easy for users to find the tools and information they need. Freelancers can accept or decline job offers directly from their dashboards, while clients can send out job requests. This setup encourages smooth communication between both parties. The administrator oversees all these activities, ensuring that everything runs smoothly and handling any issues that come up. The platform uses "routing" to guide users through different features, ensuring easy and intuitive navigation. A combination of CSS and JavaScript is used to make the website look good and be responsive, so users can easily browse on different devices. This design not only makes the platform visually appealing but also improves its usability.

4. Results and Discussion

The freelancing platform made it easy for clients and the freelancers to connect. Separate login pages kept things clear, and the job posting and application features were simple to use. Users liked the clean design and search options, which made finding jobs easier. Overall, the platform successfully helps clients find skilled freelancers, with a room to add new features like payment options and advanced search tools in the future

4.1. Preparation of Figures

The figures below represent the operation and the embedding of the various components of the working system of the freelancing platform.

4.1.1. Formatting Figures

Deployment Diagram: The deployment diagram illustrates the physical arrangement of the software and hardware components in the freelancing platform, showing how different parts are distributed across servers and interact through communication paths. Users access the platform via a client device using a web browser, which communicates with the web server hosting the Web Application. This application serves as the interface where users can check job postings, manage applications, and perform other tasks. The web server forwards requests to the application server,

which hosts core services like the API service. This includes the Authentication Service, which manages user logins and ensures only authorized access; the Job Management Service, which handles job-related functions such as posting jobs, applying, and project tracking; the Payment Processing Service, which manages payments and transactions between freelancers and clients; and the Notification Service, which sends updates about job offers, payments, or project status to users. The application server communicates with the database server, which stores all the data necessary for platform operations. The database server is divided into several databases: the User Database, which stores user profiles and account information; the Job Database, which keeps job listings and application data; the Application Database, which holds general operational data; and the Payment Database, which records financial transactions and payments.

Figure 1: Deployment Diagram of Freelancing Platform

Component Diagram: This diagram shows how the components of the freelancing platform are organized and connected through dependencies and interfaces. For the platform, the frontend consists of four main components, which are linked to several backend components. The Login Page is connected to the Authentication Service and the User Database. This allows users to securely log in, verify their identity, and access the platform. The Job Listings Page is linked to the Job Management Service and the Job Database. This allows freelancers to view available jobs, and clients to manage their postings. The system retrieves the job information from the database and displays it in the listings. The Application Form component connects to the Job Management Service and the Application Database. Freelancers can apply for jobs through the form, and the system stores their applications in the database. On the backend, several services work together such as The API Service serves as the connection point between the frontend and backend. The Notification Service is linked to the Notification Gateway, ensuring users receive timely updates about jobs, payments, or other important actions.

Figure 2: Component diagram of Freelancing Platform

Activity Diagram: The diagram shows how the freelancing platform works step by step. Users start by going to the user interface and visiting the login page, where they enter their credentials to be checked by the authentication service. After logging in successfully, freelancers go to the job listings page to look at available jobs, which come from the job database through the job management service. When a freelancer finds a job they like, they fill out an application form, which sends the information to the job management service and saves the details in the application database. If a client is involved, they can make payments through the payment processing service, and the payment details are stored in the payment database. Throughout this process, the notification service keeps users informed about job offers, application updates, or payment confirmations. The API service makes sure all parts of the platform work together smoothly, allowing easy communication between the front end and back end for a better user experience.

Figure 3: Activity diagram of Freelancing Platform

5. Conclusions

The online freelancing platform is designed to make it easier for freelancers and businesses to connect and work together. It helps freelancers find job opportunities that match their skills, while businesses can quickly find the right people to complete their projects. The platform uses a simple design and modern tools to speed up the process, allowing clients to post jobs and freelancers to respond quickly. This saves both sides a lot of time and effort in finding the right fit. The platform is especially important in today's job market, where more people are choosing freelance work over traditional jobs. It provides a central place for freelancers and clients to meet, solving common problems like finding the right job, building trust, and keeping communication clear. By bringing everyone together in one place, the platform helps create strong working relationships. However, the platform does have some challenges. For example, users need a stable internet connection to access it, and sometimes there are delays in sending notifications about new job postings or updates. In conclusion, the freelancing platform is a great solution for today's changing work environment. It shows how technology can help connect freelancers with clients, making it easier for both to find opportunities and get work done. With ongoing improvements, like better job-matching systems and communication tools, the platform will continue to grow and support freelancers and businesses in building successful working relationships.

6. Declarations

6.1. Study Limitations

None

6.2. Acknowledgements

None

6.3. Funding source

None

6.4. Competing Interests

The authors, hereby declare that there are no competing interests

7. Human and Animal Related Study

This study does not involve the collection of any physical data from humans or animals, nor does it require them to undergo extensive testing or provide samples of their bodily fluids, secretions, or excretions.

7.1. Informed Consent

All tests were conducted with the consent of participants' legal guardians.

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